

ROLE OF RASAYAN THERAPY IN ENHANCING POST-OPERATIVE RECOVERY IN PERIANAL ABSCESS-A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Anorectal diseases, including fissures, fistula-in-ano, hemorrhoids, perianal abscesses, often present with pain, bleeding, and impaired quality of life. Conventional treatment focuses on surgical intervention and analgesia, yet recurrence and post-operative morbidity remain challenges. **Rasāyana therapy**, a branch of Ayurveda aimed at rejuvenation and immunomodulation, may support tissue healing and inflammation control. We report a case where an integrated Ayurvedic approach with Rasāyana therapy contributed to clinical improvement in an post operative anorectal condition.

KEYWORDS: Perianal abscess, Post -operative recovery, Rasayan herbs, Wound healing, Integrative Medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Anorectal diseases such as hemorrhoids, fistula-in-ano, fissure-in-ano, anorectal abscess, rectal prolapse are common conditions that significantly affect quality of life. In Ayurveda, these disorders are described under various headings like *Arsha* (hemorrhoids), *Bhagandara* (fistula-in-ano), *Parikartika* (fissure-in-ano), *Gudagata vidradhi*^[1] (perianal abscess). Alongside surgical and para-surgical measures like *Ksharasutra* therapy, Ayurveda also offers a time tested framework for *Paschat Karma* that emphasizes not only physical healing but also mental and emotional well-being.

Rasayan therapy plays an important supportive and restorative role.

Modern pharmacological studies have substantiated the role of several *Rasayana herbs* in wound healing, anti-inflammatory action, collagen remodeling, pain mitigation, mental resilience.

Concept of Rasayan Therapy

The term *Rasayana* is derived from “*Rasa*” (nutritive fluid) and “*Ayana*” (pathway). It refers to therapeutic measures that enhance tissue nourishment, longevity, immunity, and vitality.^[2] *Sushruta Samhita* describes *Rasayana* as a means to strengthen body tissues (*Dhatus*), improve digestion (*Agni*), and balance *Doshas*.^[3]

In anorectal diseases, Rasayan therapy helps by

- Enhancing wound healing
- Reducing inflammation
- Preventing infection
- Strengthening rectal mucosa
- Improving bowel habits
- Preventing recurrence

CASE PRESENTATION**Patient Demographic Details****Table no. 1: The demographic details of the patient are tabulated.**

Sr.no	Demographic Details	
1.	Name	abc
2.	Age	45 yrs
3.	Sex	Male
4.	Address	Pune
5.	Socio economic status	Lower middle class

Chief complaints**Table no. 2: Chief and associated symptoms of the patient are tabulated.**

Sr.no	Symptoms	severity	duration
1.	Throbbing pain at perianal region	06(VAS)	2 weeks
2.	Difficulty to sit		2 weeks
3.	Unable to sleep		2 weeks
4.	Pain increases at defecation	07(VAS)	2 weeks

History of Present Illness

The patient reported gradual onset of pain and swelling around the anal region. Pain increased during defecation. Mild fever and malaise were present. No history of diabetes or tuberculosis.

Case History**Table no. 3: History of the patient is tabulated.**

Sr.no	Heads	Duration
1.	Fever(low grade)	On and off since 1week
2.	Surgical history	No any
3.	Medical history	No any
3.	Addiction	No any
4.	Occupation	Vegetable vendor

Local Examination

-Inspection: Swelling and erythema noted at 5 o'clock position around the anal verge. No visible discharge.
 - Palpation: Tender, fluctuant mass palpable at the site of swelling, with surrounding induration and warmth.
 -Temperature: 99.8°F
 - Digital Rectal Examination (DRE): Deferred due to severe pain; not performed to avoid discomfort.
 - Other: No signs of fistula formation.

Lab Investigations

Hb-13.2gm % TLC- 13,500/cumm P- 78% L-30 % E-02% M-02% B-00%
 Platelets- 1,90,000/cumm BSL-R-98 mg/dl Serum
 Creatinine-1.2 mg/dl
 HIV -Negative HBsAG & Anti HCV- Negative

Diagnosis

Perianal abscess at 5 o'clock position.

Ayurvedic Diagnosis

Guda Vidradhi

Surgical Intervention

Incision and Drainage under Spinal Anaesthesia

Rasayana Intervention

From Postoperative Day 1, the following regimen was introduced alongside conventional antibiotics, analgesics, and sitz baths.

A] BAHYA CHIKITSA**1. Panchavalkala Decoction**

Sitz bath BID.

2. Sarivamula Taila (*Hemidesmus Indicus*)

Topically.

B] ABHYANTAR CHIKITSA**1. Amalaki Rasayana (*Emblca officinalis*)**

Dose: 10 g daily with lukewarm water

Action: Antioxidant, promotes collagen synthesis, Pitta pacifying.

2. Guduchi Ghanavati (*Tinospora cordifolia*)

Dose: 500 mg twice daily

Action: Immunomodulator, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective.

3. Ashwagandha Churna (*Withania somnifera*)

Dose: 5 gm at bedtime with milk

Action: Tissue rejuvenation, improves strength, adaptogenic, anabolic.

4. Chyawanprash (Classical Rasayana formulation)

Dose: 1 teaspoon daily.

C] Satvavajaya chikitsa

Patient counselling.

D] Pathya–Apathya (Diet & Lifestyle Advice)-**Pathya**

- Warm, light, easily digestible food
- Green leafy vegetables
- Adequate hydration
- Sitz bath daily

Apathya

- Spicy, oily food
- Prolonged sitting

- Constipation
- Suppression of natural urges

OBSERVATIONS**Table no. 4: Clinical outcome is tabulated.**

Sr.no	Parameters	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3
1.	Shula (VAS)	4/10	2/10	No any
2.	Kathinya (induration)	mild	reduced	No any
3.	Cavity	Progressive regression	Progressive regression	Complete regression
4.	Vranatala(wound healing)	Improved	Progressive	Complete epithelization

Fig. 3: 3rd week**Comparative Case Summary****Without RASAYAN THERAPY**

Healing time :4 weeks

Pain(Day 7):7/10

Reoccurrence: Minor symptoms at 6 months

Analgesic use: Daily till 3 weeks

With RASAYAN THERAPY

Healing time:3 weeks

Pain(Day 7):4/10

Reoccurrence: None

Analgesic use: Tapered after 1 week

Mechanism of Action (Ayurvedic Perspective)

Rasayana drugs are believed to:-

- *Agni Sandhookshana*- promoting digestion and metabolism
- *Sroto Prakritisthapana*- promoting competence of srotas
- *Dosha Samyakaram*- prevents imbalance of doshas, especially pitta and vata, which aggravate post-surgical inflammation and pain
- *Dhatu Vardhana*- improving dhatuposhana.
- *Mana Prasannata*- promoting mental endurance
- *Ojas Vriddhi* - Boosts immunity and vitality^[4]

Pharmacological Actions of Rasayana Components

1. *Amalaki (Emblica officinalis)*: Enhances fibroblast activity and wound contraction, increases hydroxyproline content in granulation tissue.^[5]

2. *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia)*: Inhibits TNF- α and IL-6 pathways, improves wound tensile strength.^[6]

3. *Ashwagandha (Withania somnifera)*: Lowers systemic inflammation via NF- κ B inhibition, supports nerve repair and mucosal regeneration, anxiolytics, adaptogenic, reduces cortisol.^[7]

4. *Panchavalka*: Possesses antimicrobial, astringent, and granulation-supporting properties.

5. *Sarivamula(Hemidesmus indicus)*: Tridosha shaman, possess antimicrobial properties.^[8]

DISCUSSION

According to *Charaka Samhita*, *Rasayana* therapy enhances *Vyadhikshamatva (immunity)* and promotes tissue regeneration.

In anorectal abscess, after surgical drainage, Rasayana helps

- Faster wound healing
- Prevention of fistula formation
- Reducing recurrence
- Strengthening anorectal tissue

- The integration of *Rasayana* therapy demonstrates the benefits in postoperative care by enhancing faster tissue healing, improving immune response, reducing inflammation, and supporting mental resilience.
 - Additionally, adoption of a *Sattvik* lifestyle contributes to psychological stability and improved recovery outcomes.
 - These outcomes suggest that Ayurvedic rejuvenative protocols may serve as effective adjuncts in surgical recovery.
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Advantages of *Rasayan* Therapy in Anorectal Diseases

- Holistic approach
- Reduces recurrence
- Improves immunity
- Enhances overall health
- Suitable for long-term management
- Supports both conservative and surgical treatments

CONCLUSION

Integration of *Rasayan* therapy with contemporary postoperative management may offer a holistic approach to patient recovery by addressing both physical and mental dimensions of health. The convergence of traditional Ayurvedic wisdom can enhance post operative outcomes, promote faster recovery and improve overall quality of life. Greater recognition of *Rasayan* therapy is therefore advocated.

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